

EFFECT OF MOLARITY ON DEVELOPMENT OF FLY ASH BASED GEOPOLYMER HIGH PERFORMANCE CONCRETE

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ABSTRACT

This paper evaluates the effect for molarity of alkaline solution on development of Geopolymer High Performance Concrete (GHPC). The important parameters like alkaline/binder ratio (AL/B), molarity of alkaline solution, curing temperature and fineness of binder plays an important role in the development of GHPC. Alkaline binder solutions like Sodium Hydroxide and Sodium Silicate were used in present investigation. Molarity of alkaline solution of Sodium Hydroxide was varied from M10, M12, M14 and M16. Alkaline binder ratio was considered as 0.35 and processed fly ash (FA) as a binder was used for development of GHPC in the present investigation and tested for compressive strength after 3 hours, 8 hours and 24 hours oven heat curing period. Oven heat curing temperature was maintained at 90°C. It was observed that as the molarity of alkaline solution increases, compressive strength of cured geopolymer samples also increases moderately but workability of fresh geopolymer concrete mixes reduced from molarity M14 to M16.

KEYWORDS

Geopolymer High Performance Concrete, molarity, fly ash, oven heat curing, compressive strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

As infrastructural activities are going on large scale all over the world, demand of cement increasing day by day. Due to this growing demand of cement, concrete industry can't able to fulfill the demand as per requirement in specific duration. Since last decade, a more attention has attracted amongst researcher towards the development of alkali activated concrete commercially named as geopolymer concrete. In 1978, Davidovits proposed that binders could be produced by polymerization process of alkaline liquids with processed industrial wastes like Fly Ash (FA), Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBFS), Metakaoline, Rice Husk Ash (RHA), etc. He termed these binders as geo-polymers. The binders bind the aggregates together to form geopolymer concrete [3-5]. The primary requirements for creating stable geopolymers are that the starting materials be highly amorphous, have a significant amount of reactive glassy component, require little water, and quickly release aluminium. The geopolymer made from fly ash was stronger and more durable than the geopolymer made from metakaolin. Slag-based geopolymers have been found to be more acid-resistant and have higher early strength than metakaolin and fly ash-based geopolymers [2]. At 65 °C and 85 °C, Polomo et al. evaluated the curing of alkali activated fly ash-based concrete. The compressive strength of geopolymer (8–12 Molarity) treated at 85 °C for 24 Hrs. was found to be significantly higher than that of those

cured at 65 °C. When curing time was increased after 24 hours, the increase in strength was noticeably less. Longer term curing at a higher temperature led to samples failing at a later age, due to the thermolysis of the Si-O-Al-O bond [6].

The objective of developing this sustainable geopolymer concrete was to reutilize the by products from industrial sources effectively and make the world of concrete more greener. Geopolymer concrete technology could significantly helped in reducing the carbon footprint.

2. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

2.1. Materials

The following materials were used for present experimental study.

2.1.1. Fly ash

The processed fly ash under trade name as Pozzocrete 100 processed by Ambuja Cement Ltd. under unit Dirk India Pvt. Ltd. was used for present experimental work having important properties as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Important properties of processed fly ash

Test No.	Testing parameters	Unit	Test Results
1	Fineness – specific surface by Blaine’s Permeability Method (Min.)	m ² /kg	638
2	ROS #350 (45 MIC) (Max.)	%	0.03
3	Lime Reactivity (Min.)	N/mm ²	7.47
10	Total Chlorides	%	0.023

2.1.2. Sodium Silicate solution

Alkaline binder with Sodium Silicate in the form of liquid with weight ratio of Na₂O: SiO₂ as 1:2.17 was used for present experimental study.

2.1.3. Sodium Hydroxide solution

Alkaline binder as Sodium Hydroxide in the form of flakes was used with minimum assay more than 96% was used for present experimental study.

2.1.4. Potable Water

Potable water was used for present experimental study.

2.1.5. Superplasticizer

Naphthalene based super plasticizer was used to enhance the workability and reduce the water content.

2.1.7. Fine aggregate and coarse aggregate

As per BIS: 383 fine aggregate with fineness modulus as 2.65 and well graded coarse aggregate of 20 mm and 10 mm sizes with a combination of 60:40 in percentages were used for present experimental study.

2.2. Experimental study

2.2.1. Preparation of alkaline solution

The alkaline binder solutions of Sodium Hydroxide and Sodium Silicate was used. Molarity of Sodium Hydroxide solution used maintained was 10M, 12M, 14M and 16M. Care should be taken while preparing the Sodium Hydroxide solution, as significant amount of heat was evolved during solution preparation.

2.2.2. Casting and curing of geopolymer high performance concrete

Continuous mixing in rotating drum mixer should deliver uniform mixing. The table vibrator was employed for few seconds after placing freshly mixed geopolymer concrete into cube molds of 150 x 150 x 150 mm size. After 24 hours, the cast specimens are demolded. The demolded specimens are kept in oven at 90°C for 3 hours, 8 hours and 24 hours as curing period. Then it removed from the oven and cooled to room temperature.

2.2.3. Workability of geopolymer high strength concrete

To ensure the workability of concrete mixes naphthalene based superplasticizer was added with respect to binder content as per mix proportioning. Workability can be measured with the help of flow table apparatus. As a result, Figure 1 depicts the flow table apparatus.

Figure 1. Flow table apparatus with fresh geopolymer concrete

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Experimental results for geopolymer high performance concrete

It was observed that freshly mixed fly ash based geopolymer concrete was viscous and cohesive. As alkaline solution was used, it looks sticky, glassy appearance and dark in color. Workability of freshly mix geopolymer concrete was measured by using flow table apparatus as per BIS:5512 and BIS:1727.

After measuring the workability, freshly mix geopolymer concrete with cube molds of 150 x 150 x 150 mm size were cast and kept it for 24 hours as a rest period. After demoulding of

concrete cube molds carefully, the cube specimens were kept in oven for heat curing duration of 3 hours, 8 hours and 24 hours at 90 °C. Cured concrete samples were tested under Compression Testing Machine (CTM capacity - 3000 kN). The average compressive strength was considered for every three cubes with 3 hours, 8 hours and 24 hours heat curing duration for different Molairty of solution. Alkaline binder ratio (AL/B) kept as 0.35 for all design mixes

The experimental results have shown in tabular form as below in **Table 2** and **Table 3**

Table 2. Experimental results for fly ash based GHPC without superplasticizer

Observation	Data considered in mix design	Fly ash based GHPC results with different molarity mixes			
		M10	M12	M14	M16
Workability (flow in %)	Medium	Very High	Very High	Very High	Very High
Rest period	24 hours	24 hours	24 hours	24 hours	24 hours
Curing Temperature	90°C	90°C	90°C	90°C	90°C
Minimum mass density (kg/m ³)	2400	2512.4	2536.3	2550.6	2567.2
Average compression strength at 3 hours curing period in MPa	30-40 %	18.48	21.78	20.62	24.53
Average compression strength at 8 hours curing period in MPa	60-80 %	32.45	39.55	41.56	44.50
Average compression strength at 24 hours curing period in MPa	95-100 %	61.24	70.22	71.54	76.54

Table 3. Experimental results for fly ash based GHPC with 2% superplasticizer

Observation	Data considered in mix design	Fly ash based GHPC results with different molarity mixes			
		M10	M12	M14	M16
Workability (flow in %)	Medium	Very High	Very High	Very High	Very High
Rest period	24 hours	24 hours	24 hours	24 hours	24 hours
Curing Temperature	90°C	90°C	90°C	90°C	90°C
Minimum mass density (kg/m ³)	2400	2532.7	2543.1	2557.2	2568.8
Average compression strength at 3 hours curing period in MPa	30-40 %	20.12	23.15	25.67	24.32
Average compression strength at 8 hours curing period in MPa	60-80 %	38.42	45.31	42.20	47.58
Average compression strength at 24 hours curing period in MPa	95-100 %	63.28	71.21	72.60	74.84

Figure 2. Comparison of average compressive strength of geopolymer Geopolymer high performance concrete (GHPC) with different molarity mixes and superplasticizer

Figure 3. Different molarity mixes and target compressive strength with and without superplasticizer

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the experimental investigation for development of fly ash based geopolymer high performance concrete with and without using superplasticizer for alkaline binder ratio as 0.35 for different molarity mixes. The following conclusions can be drawn from the experimental investigation.

For AL/B ratio of 0.35, the fly ash based Geopolymer High Performance Concrete [GHPC] after 24 hours (One day) heat curing period with target compressive strength of more than 65 MPa achieved for the proposed concrete mix proportioning.

As molarity of alkaline solution increases, compressive strength also increases marginally but workability goes on decreases due to more causticness of solution

For higher molarity of 14M and 16M, mixes were found very sticky and sets rapidly.

With respect to different molarity of alkaline solution, optimum value for molarity of alkaline solution obtained as 12M for development of fly ash based GHPC.

Superplasticizer have no any effect on improving compressive strength of GHPC as per experimental results obtained. It was used for enhancing workability purpose only

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